

MS3 Integrations with alternative initialisation strategies

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Executive Summary

This report summarises developments and experiments contributing to the ASPECT Task 1.2, *Explore novel initialisation and forecast generation strategies for more reliable predictions by reducing forecast drift*. Initialised predictions are often affected by initialisation shock and subsequent drift, as a consequence of unbalanced initial conditions. This work therefore develops and tests prediction system improvements to generate more balanced initial conditions, and thereby reduce the drift in the predictions. This includes improved ocean initialisation, testing the impact of the ocean observing system, selecting SST products for the early satellite period, testing how model bias affects forecast skill, developing and testing coupled atmosphere-ocean nudging to produce the initial conditions, and model upgrades. These developments lead to modest improvements of the predictions, but we also acknowledge the complexity of the prediction systems where improvements in some aspects do not necessarily translate into enhanced skill. These experiments are now underpinning the development of new versions of operation prediction systems by several project partners.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a bandwidth diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing method enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Heading 1

1.1 Work at ECMWF

In this section we present work carried out at ECMWF related with WP1 Task1.2. The work is part of larger effort along different directions, including ECMWF core activities and DestinE. The contribution of ASPECT has been to find synergies between efforts, design experiments and interpret results so the outcomes can be relevant for the wider ASPECT and climate communities.

1.1.1 Ocean initialization via 3D nudging to external product

In the context of predictions with coupled models beyond a few days, the ocean initial conditions are a particularly meaningful ingredient, since the ocean memory dominates the long term predictability of the climate system. Ocean initial conditions are generally obtained by blending the outcomes of an ocean model forced by the best estimation of surface fluxes with in-situ and satellite observations of the ocean, such as temperature and salinity profiles

from a variety of platforms, altimeter-derived sea level, sea surface temperature and sea-ice concentration. For instance, in the current ECMWF system (ORAS5, Zuo et al 2019), the ocean initial conditions are obtained by combining the information provided by the NEMO ocean model (NEMO3.4, LIM2), running at a nominal $\frac{1}{4}^\circ$ (~25km at the equator) resolution and forced by ERA-Interim, with ocean observations via the NEMOVAR data assimilation system. Ocean data assimilation systems are complex and expensive, and only a few (mostly operational) institutions have the capability to use them routinely.

In the atmosphere model world, where the adjustment time scales are short (order of hours), it is possible (and current practice) to use the initial conditions obtained with a given model and data assimilation system to initialize forecast at a different resolution or indeed other atmospheric models. This is not the case for the ocean: the slow time scales of the ocean together with the existence of continental boundaries implies that transferring ocean initial conditions obtained with a model at a given resolution to a different ocean model, or different resolution is not trivial. This is a serious handicap for i) the usability of ocean reanalysis (which are mostly used only by the same -very few- groups that produce them), and ii) for the production of new ocean reanalysis, which have to be produced sequentially, and makes the experimentation and preparations of new multi-decadal ocean reanalysis products very slow. If we could find a method which allows the initialization of an ocean model from an external reference product, this will increase the agility of the climate research (e.g faster reanalysis cycles, more experimentation with high resolution coupled forecasts), and it will facilitate the use of ocean reanalysis in the provision of climate information (e.g. initialized climate outlooks or the DestinE climate twin)

Here we explore the use **nudging** (simple Newtonian relaxation) as an affordable surrogate for ocean data assimilation. The input to the nudging (reference dataset) are 3D gridded ocean temperature, salinity, sea-ice concentration and thickness from an external ocean reanalysis or objectively gridded fields (such as EN4, where no ocean model is involved). Nudging provides a relatively **quickly-implementable and lightly-intrusive** (code-wise) solution for evaluating the effects of high-resolution ocean initial conditions, so the method can be easily used by different research groups. It also provides **flexibility** regarding the choice of reference dataset.

Here we have conducted studies on the sensitivity of the solution to the relaxation strength, which will influence the fit to the reference data and will also have implications in the ocean transports. The Control experiment is the NEMO4 model version forced by ERA5 hourly data and very weak relaxation (3-years) to the WOA18 climatology, with a similar configuration of that used for the upcoming ECMWF ocean reanalysis ORAS6 (Zuo et al 2024). The Control experiment has been run for the period 1970-2010. The reference dataset is EN4 objectively gridded analysis, which provides monthly means of temperature and salinity for the 3D global ocean. We conduct a set of 10-year long nudging experiments initialized from Control at different times (1982,1990,1995,2000) and assess how the results converge depending on the initialization start date. For each initial date there are two experiments: strong relaxation (30-days time scale) and weak relaxation (180-days except for the Southern Ocean, where the relaxation is 360-days). Below we only illustrate the results for the experiments initialized in 1990 and 1995, but the conclusions hold for other start dates.

Figure 1 shows the effect of the relaxation and start date on the temperature field. The figure shows the 0-1000m RMS error of the temperature of the different experiments with respect to

the in-situ observations, averaged for different areas: global, tropics, northern extratropics and southern extratropics. As expected, the relaxation reduces the RMS error w.r.t the RMS error of the Control (dashed black line), and the reduction of the error is more visible with the stronger relaxation. The reduction of the error happens quite quickly, usually in less than one year, confirming that it is relatively easy to constrain the large scale ocean temperature field. This is in principle good news for climate predictions and for parallel productions of ocean reanalysis.

hyqr sea water potential temperature OUTER RMS depth0-1000m

Fig 1. Temperature RMS error of the different experiments with respect to the in-situ observations, averaged over the upper 1000m and for different areas: global, tropics, northern extratropics and southern extratropics.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the ocean transports across key regions (Drake Passage, Indonesian Throughflow, Barent and Florida Straits) for experiments initialized in 1990 and 1995, with strong and weak relaxation. Also shown is the Control experiment, from which the different nudging experiments were initialized. External references are ORAS5 (blue line), which uses the same ocean resolution but different model version and bathymetry (as well as data assimilation), and the Rapid estimation of the Florida Strait transport (black solid line). For the Drake and Florida Straits, the value of the transport is primary dominated by the relaxation time scales. The Indonesian Throughflow transport is mostly dependent of the model configuration, which is different in NEMO4 than in the version used for ORAS5. The Barent-strait transport is relatively well constrained in all the cases, although the model version seems to be also the most dominant factor.

i9jd zonal transport depth: 5596-5596 m with 12-month running mean

Fig 2. Ocean transports across key regions (Drake Passage, Indonesian Throughflow, Barent and Florida Straits) for experiments initialized in 1990 and 1995, with strong and weak relaxation. Also shown is the Control experiment (orange line, labeled as weak_WOA18_ndg), from which the different nudging experiments were initialized. [Note the different colour coding w.r.t. Fig 1]. External references are ORAS5 (blue line), which uses the same ocean resolution but different model version and bathymetry (as well as data assimilation), and the Rapid estimation of the Florida Strait transport (black solid line).

The strength of the relaxation produces opposite outcomes in the Drake and Florida straits. Strong relaxation increases the Drake transports, producing unrealistic values. In contrast, the Florida transports are reduced with strong relaxation. One possible explanation is that the balance in the $\frac{1}{4}$ degree NEMO configuration is mainly geostrophic, and does not include satisfactory the contribution of eddies. Weaker relaxation allows the model to find its own equilibrium, producing more realistic transport values.

We also that there is rapid initialization shock (the solution for the different relaxations diverges in the first year), to then converge to their own equilibrium in about 4-5 years for the weak relaxation experiments, about 1-2 years for the strong relaxation experiments.

The impact of the relaxation time-scale on the ocean transports and its sensitivity to ocean model resolution deserves more attention. If the reason for the strong impact on transports is the contribution of the eddie field, it should be possible to choose the a spatially dependent nudging time scale that takes into account the unrepresented eddies for a given model resolution. In addition, one could explore alternative methods, such as the so-called “replay” approach (Sun et al 2025). Work is ongoing along these directions.

1.1.2 Evaluating the impact of the Ocean Observing System

Ocean observations are essential for ocean predictions and also contribute to weather and climate predictions based on coupled atmosphere-ocean models, especially at subseasonal and longer time scales. However, developing and sustaining the ocean observation network requires a huge amount of human and financial resources. Therefore, the ocean observation network should be designed to efficiently acquire effective observation data, and their adequacy should be continually evaluated (e.g., Balmaseda et al 2009, Fujii et al., 2019). Especially nowadays, many ocean observing systems (e.g., the global Argo array, mooring arrays, ocean observing satellites, ocean gliders, and autonomous underwater vehicles) require scientific support for their usefulness in order to sustain them.

There are several strategies to demonstrate the importance of observational data and to scientifically support the maintenance and expansion of the ocean observation network. Among them, observing system experiments (OSEs) are widely used in order to evaluate the importance of the ocean observation data and the effectiveness of ocean observing systems for ocean predictions. OSEs are data assimilation and prediction experiments in which specific observation types are excluded from or added to the data being assimilated, and the impact of the observation types is assessed by comparing it with regular data assimilation and prediction. Observing system simulation experiments (OSSEs), which are the same as OSEs but use synthetic observation data generated from a reference simulation instead of real observation data, are also performed for evaluating the future observing system or proposing a new design of an observation network. However, the results of OSEs and OSSEs severely depend on the property of the system, including systematic errors of the system (i.e., model biases), physical parameterizations, and data assimilation schemes applied in the system, as demonstrated in previous studies. Therefore, it is preferable to conduct the OSEs/OSSEs using multiple prediction systems in order to mitigate the differences in evaluations caused by the system dependency and to draw robust and reliable conclusions.

The United Nations (UN) Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, that is, the UN Ocean Decade ([UNESCO-IOC, 2021](https://oceandecade.org/); see also <https://oceandecade.org/>), provides a good opportunity to make a close collaboration between ocean observing and ocean and coupled prediction communities, as well as among various groups in the ocean prediction community, for evaluating the importance of ocean observation systems and co-designing the future evolution of the ocean observing network. “Synergistic Observing Network for Ocean Prediction (SynObs)” was launched as a UN Ocean Decade Project in 2022 to take advantage of this collaborative opportunity (see <https://oceanpredict.org/un-decade-of-ocean-science/synobs-2/>). SynObs is currently coordinating the flagship OSEs/OSSEs, a collaborative OSEs/OSSEs using multiple ocean and subseasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) prediction systems to make robust and reliable evaluations that are seen across a variety of substantially varying ocean data assimilation and prediction systems.

The SynObs flagship OSEs/OSSEs comprises ocean prediction (OP) OSEs/OSSEs, and S2S OSEs. The OP OSEs/OSSEs are designed to evaluate the impacts of existing observing systems on ocean predictions, particularly those made by relatively high-resolution ocean data assimilation and prediction systems. The S2S OSEs are designed to evaluate observation impacts on atmosphere and ocean predictions at S2S timescales. They cover a long analysis period (2003–2022, with possible extension to 2023), and execution of 1-month or 4-month forecasts with coupled ocean–atmosphere models is also encouraged. ASPECT contributes

to this international initiative by conducting S2S OSEs with a version of the upcoming ECMWF ocean reanalysis system ORAS6 and assessing the impact of the ocean observing system in reanalysis and seasonal reforecasts.

The Table below shows the experimental protocol for OSEs in the SynObs project. The data will be publicly available, and the analysis of results will be done along thematic areas (Marine Heat Wave, Ocean Heat Uptake, climate trends) through international groups of experts. We refer to [Fuji et al 2024](#) for more details on the SynObs project. ECMWF has conducted and submitted data for experiments CNTL, NoArgo, NoInsitu, Free. The rest of the experiments are ongoing, expected to be completed by the end of 2025.

	Name	Configuration of OSEs						
1	CNTL	Ocean model		SST	Argo 80%	Mooring	Other TS	Nadir altimeter
2	NoAlt	Ocean model		SST	Argo 80%	Mooring	Other TS	
3	NoArgo	Ocean model		SST		Mooring	Other TS	Nadir altimeter
4	NoMooring	Ocean model		SST	Argo 80%		Other TS	Nadir altimeter
5	NoSST	Ocean model			Argo 80%	Mooring	Other TS	Nadir altimeter
6	NoInsitu	Ocean model		SST				Nadir altimeter
7	SSTonly	Ocean model		SST				
8	Free	Ocean model						
9	HalfArgo	Ocean model		SST	Argo 40%	Mooring	Other TS	Nadir altimeter
10	Oper	Ocean model	Operational setting	SST	Argo 80%	Mooring	Other TS	Nadir altimeter

The number of the leftmost column indicates the order of priority for the OP-OSE protocol, while the right column lists the guidance for the S2S-OSE protocol. Settings or observations in color-filled cells are adopted or used.

OP, ocean prediction; OSEs, observing system experiments; S2S, subseasonal-to-seasonal; SST, Sea Surface Temperature; TS, temperature and salinity.

1.1.3 Selection of SST products suitable for reanalysis in the early satellite period

SST observational datasets are key for the production of ocean and atmospheric reanalysis. The upcoming ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis (ERA6) will include an element of coupling with the ocean, in that it will see the SST coming from the upcoming ECMWF ocean reanalysis ORAS6 ([Zuo et al 2024](#)). Daily Level 4 SST data are required for assimilation in ORAS6. There are several different L4 SST datasets that cover the ORAS6 time period, and it is important to choose products for consistency and accuracy. The three principal time periods to consider are pre-satellite, post-satellite, and near real time. The operational dataset that is available with 1 day lag is OSTIA near-real time operational analysis (NRT), the same product that is used in near real time for ORAS5 (Zuo et al., 2018) and ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020). For the post-satellite period, the datasets to assess are Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) reprocessed (REP), European Space Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative (CCI) v3 (Embury et al., 2024), Japan Meteorological Administration (JMA) Centennial In Situ Observation-Based Estimates of SST version 2.9.2 (COBE-SST2) (Hirahara et al., 2014), and ERA5, which has SST boundary conditions from the Met Office Hadley Centre Sea Ice and SST dataset (HadISST2.1.1.0) (Titchner & Rayner, 2014) from January 1979 to August 2007, and from OSTIA NRT from September 2007 onwards (Hersbach et al., 2020). ESA CCI v3 is a newly released dataset that supersedes the v2.1 product and is a Climate Data Record (CDR) from 1980 to 2021, with data from 2022 onwards provided as an interim CDR, 1 month behind real time.

The post-satellite period includes March and April 1982, when the Mexican volcano, El Chichón, erupted, and this coincided with the initiation of the strong 1982-1983 El Niño event. It has been shown that the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) instrument is significantly affected by aerosols in the stratosphere, such as those produced by the eruption of El Chichón. Figure 3 shows the global mean (60°N-60°S) SST from each of these L4 products from 1982-2000. It is clear that OSTIA REP exhibits large erroneous jumps in global mean SST during the early part of this time period, particularly around 1982/1983, which are not present in the other datasets. Despite also using satellite data, the recent ESA CCI v3 dataset and ERA5 (HadISST2.1.1.0) do not experience these large jumps. COBE-SST2 uses only in situ data, and so effects of aerosol from such volcanoes are not expected.

Figure 3. Global mean SST (60°N-60°S) of OSTIA REP, COBE-SST2, ESA CCI v3, and ERA5. ERA5 has SST boundary conditions from HadISST2.1.1.0 in this time period shown.

ESA CCI v3 is the most recent L4 SST product released, is provided at high resolution (0.05 degrees), and extends for over 40 years. Following careful analysis of all potential L4 SST products, it has been decided that ESA CCI v3 is assimilated in ORAS6 from 1980 to 2023, as the most accurate and consistent product.

Now that the SST products have been chosen for 1980 to present, the choice of SST product for the pre-satellite period is being considered. There is a newly released dataset, HadISST2.4, being examined along other, older datasets, such as HadISST2 and COBE-SST2. As well as choosing the SST product for assimilation, experiments are being conducted to ascertain the sampling and error characteristics to implement. Several ocean reanalysis experiments are on-going exploring different options. These experiments will later be used to initialize seasonal forecasts and assess the impact of the choice of SST product on the seasonal forecast skill.

1.1.4 Assessing the impact of model bias on forecast skill

The impact of model biases on sub-seasonal forecast skill has been evaluated in the European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) sub-seasonal forecasting system using a relaxation experiment where the nudging was performed towards bias corrected integrations of the same model (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Description of the 3 steps for the bias corrected relaxation experiments.

The relaxation was performed regionally or globally but only for the very large scale. As expected, this methodology significantly reduces model biases over the areas where the nudging was applied (Figure 5a). Remarkably, the experiments also display significantly improved forecast skill in predicting the anomalies at a lead time of 3 to 4 weeks, particularly over the Northern Extratropics (Figure 5b), where sub-seasonal forecast skill has been stagnant at this time range over the past 20 years in the ECMWF operational sub-seasonal forecasting system.

Figure 5: Vertical and meridional cross-section of temperature biases relative to ERA5 in Global experiment (top left panel), Control experiment (top middle panel) and difference between Global and Control (bottom left panel). The right panel shows a scorecard for experiment Global (with 5 days relaxation time scale), compared to Control. The abbreviation w1 corresponds to week 1 (days 5–11), w2 corresponds to week 2 (days 12–18), w3 corresponds to week 3 (days 19–25), and w4 corresponds to week 4 (days 26–32) from the start date. The following variables are verified: total precipitation (tp), 2-m temperature (t2m), surface temperature (stemp), sea surface temperature (sst), mean sea level pressure (mslp), temperature at 50 hPa (t50), horizontal wind at 50 hPa (u50), meridional wind at 50 hPa (v50), streamfunction at 200 hPa (sf200), velocity potential at 200 hPa (vp200), temperature at 200 hPa (t200).

hPa (t200), horizontal wind at 200 hPa (u200), meridional wind at 200 hPa (v200), geopotential at 500 hPa (z500), temperature at 500 hPa (t500), horizontal wind at 500 hPa (u500), meridional wind at 500 hPa (v500), temperature at 850 hPa (t850), horizontal wind at 850 hPa (u850), and meridional wind at 850 hPa (v850).

An analysis of a North Pole relaxation experiment shows that the polar relaxation impacts biases outside the region of nudging, such as the representation of the sub-tropical jet stream in the ECMWF model, reducing mid-latitude geopotential height bias and leading to a slight improvement in MJO teleconnections over the Northern Extratropics. These results set a lower threshold for predictability at the sub-seasonal time scales and indicate that there is a large potential for improving dynamical sub-seasonal forecasting skill in weeks 3 and 4 in Extratropical regions by improved treatment of model error. This work has been submitted for publication and it is currently under revision (Vitart and Balmaseda 2025).

1.2 Work at BSC

This section describes the contribution of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) to WP1 Task 1.2. It documents the experimental configurations, preliminary forecast assessments and model development carried out at BSC with the goal to improve climate predictions through physically balanced initial conditions. We test the use of coupled reconstructions to generate dynamically balanced initial conditions for initialized predictions. This work synergizes with BSC's broader efforts to enhance its operational decadal climate prediction system.

1.2.1 Evaluating the benefits of coupled nudging

Initialized climate predictions are affected by the initialization shock and subsequent drift, which limit predictability across all timescales. These effects arise in part from initializing model components close to the observed state and far from the model attractor (e.g. [Meehl et al., 2014](#)). Additionally, when generated separately, atmospheric and oceanic initial conditions can be physically inconsistent and cause an adjustment at the beginning of the forecast. Recent studies show that an initial state obtained from a coupled reconstruction can reduce these imbalances and enhance forecast reliability from seasonal to decadal timescales (Meehl et al., 2021; Bilbao et al., 2021). Motivated by these findings, BSC explored coupled reconstruction strategies with an EC-Earth3.3 decadal prediction system (Bilbao et al., 2021) to assess their impact on forecast drift and skill.

We benchmark the benefits of initializing with a coupled reconstruction against the standard uncoupled approach currently used in our prediction system, which relies on a nudging framework to produce historical ocean reconstructions forced by ERA5 reanalyses. Given that the ocean is the primary source of predictability on decadal timescales (Servonnat et al., 2015; Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2016), we have previously tested various setups, settling on nudging ocean temperature and salinity fields below the mixed layer towards the EN4 (Met Office) dataset, while at the surface they are relaxed toward ORAS5 (ECMWF). The selected configuration has a tropical buffer zone with no subsurface nudging to prevent spurious vertical velocities from occurring (Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2015). This setup was validated by running retrospective seasonal predictions with EC-Earth3.3 for the 1985–2015 period, using 5 members and a 9-month forecast range for November and May initializations. These

reforecasts provide the counterpart needed to evaluate the added value of the coupled assimilation approach.

A set of coupled reconstruction experiments was produced with EC-Earth3, applying Newtonian relaxation simultaneously in the atmosphere (towards ERA5) and the ocean. The ocean component is nudged using the setup described above, while in the atmosphere nudging is applied to temperature, vorticity and divergence with a relaxation timescale of 12 hours (the baseline configuration). Sensitivity experiments were designed to assess the impact of the vertical profile of atmospheric nudging, motivated by concerns that constraining the planetary boundary layer may inhibit fast atmospheric adjustments and contribute to initialization shock. Three representative configurations tested are: full-column nudging; nudging restricted to mid-to-upper tropospheric levels; and nudging applied over an extended tropospheric–lower stratospheric range. Simultaneously, we varied the strength of surface restoring in the ocean.

Preliminary results (see Figure 6) from the analysis did not show substantial improvements in predictive capacity over the uncoupled benchmark with EC-Earth 3.3. We evaluated the forecast skill by calculating the tos anomaly correlation coefficients with respect to ERA5 data. Compared to a simulation without atmospheric nudging, the nudging experiments exhibited higher skill persistence in the North Atlantic, while the skill persistence in the Labrador Sea declined. Time evolution of ocean surface temperature (tos) in various areas of interest, such as the North Atlantic, the Labrador Sea, Niño3 and ATL3 regions, showed no signs of initialization shocks.

Overall, the analysis suggests that the configuration with fewer nudged atmospheric levels might yield slightly better results. However, studying the Quasi-biennial Oscillation (QBO) revealed that this configuration does not correctly initialise the atmospheric oscillation, favouring the other setups that rely more on atmospheric coupled nudging. Although several other variables such as sea ice, precipitation or ocean heat content were studied, there is no definitive winning configuration.

Figure 6. Anomaly correlation coefficient against observations for sea surface temperature (SST) in the Niño3.4 region (left) and the Labrador Sea (right) for various experiments. In colour are the experimental seasonal prediction systems initialized using different coupled assimilation strategies, while the black line is for the best performing uncoupled assimilation configuration.

Consequently, the team has redirected its efforts toward developing nudged assimilation capabilities for the new version of the prediction system based on EC-Earth4, which will contribute to the upcoming Phase 7 of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP). The atmospheric component of EC-Earth4 is based on OIFS cycle 48r1 and offers more flexibility in applying nudging, allowing for a more efficient exploration of coupled assimilation potential in next-generation model development. This preliminary configuration has already been applied to conduct idealized studies of the Valencia 2024 DANA storm, investigating how the event would have developed and intensified within a context of greater global warming than the current climate.

The current assessment is based on a limited ensemble size and forecast range. Ongoing work focuses on repeating experiments with a large ensemble size in the system based on a more computationally efficient EC-Earth4. These developments aim to establish whether coupled reconstructions provide sufficient added value to justify future use in our new generation decadal prediction systems.

1.3 Work at CMCC

Within the framework of the ASPECT project, CMCC has implemented advanced land surface modeling capabilities for the new Seasonal Prediction System (SPS4). While the current implementation is focused on seasonal predictions, the methodological approach and computational framework are designed with extensibility to future earth system modeling systems.

We introduce two key innovations: the Community Land Model version 5.1 (CLM5.1) and the HYdro-Dynamic ROuting Scheme (HYDROS). CLM5.1 represents a significant advancement in land surface modeling, offering sophisticated parameterizations that capture the complex interactions between vegetation, soil, and atmospheric processes. HYDROS provides a novel approach to river transport, enabling more dynamic and responsive representations of terrestrial water dynamics.

Central to our methodology is an innovative land initialization strategy that goes beyond traditional approaches. By generating initial conditions through observed atmospheric forcings, multi-century spin-up, and controlled perturbations, we aim to provide a more physically consistent starting point for the new CMCC seasonal prediction system.

1.3.1 Model Updates and Initialization Strategy

In SPS4, CMCC introduces the Community Land Model version 5.1 (CLM5.1), a major upgrade from CLM4.5, operating at roughly $1/2^\circ$ resolution with 20 soil layers and 5 bedrock layers, and a 30-minute timestep. CLM5.1 enhances land surface dynamics by integrating dynamic land units, refined hydrology and snow processes, improved plant hydraulics, a revised nitrogen cycle, and an advanced urban module (Lawrence et al., 2019). It also applies the Anderson (1976) snow density parameterization and incorporates a tuning factor for snow aging computation (Flanner and Zender, 2006).

For river transport, SPS4 replaces the previous model with HYDROS, which dynamically calculates flow velocity using the Darcy-Weisbach equation, accounting for orographic and

hydrological complexities (Materia et al., in preparation). HYDROS runs on a 0.5° grid and receives three-hourly water routing inputs from CLM5.1, enabling a more detailed simulation of terrestrial water flows.

The land initialization strategy in SPS4 follows a carefully designed methodology that ensures both consistency and variability. The initialization begins with a multi-century spin-up that allows slow soil carbon pools to reach equilibrium. This is followed by a one-month initialization run forced by observed atmospheric conditions, which helps capture recent land surface states. A key aspect of this strategy is the generation of multiple initial conditions: three distinct land initial condition perturbations are created for each simulation, using three randomly selected members from the ERA5-EDA dataset. This approach introduces controlled variability while maintaining strong physical consistency between hindcasts and operational forecasts. The initialization includes soil moisture and snow fields derived directly from this procedure. High-frequency (3-hourly) atmospheric forcings are used to capture the complex, memory-laden dynamics of the land surface, ultimately improving the robustness and predictive skill of the seasonal forecast system.

1.3.2 Advantages of the new updates

Compared to the previous SPS3.5, the SPS4 framework introduces a substantially more rigorous and physically consistent land initialization methodology. The land initialization now leverages a set of long land-only simulations forced by atmospheric conditions from the ERA5-EDA, allowing for a better sampling of the uncertainty in the atmospheric forcing and, consequently, in soil moisture and snow fields. The updated land component CLM5.1 (instead of CLM4.5) improves the representation of many land surface features (Lawrence et al., 2019) and, thanks to its prognostic treatment of the main biogeochemical cycles (Carbon and Nitrogen, BGC configuration), it also represents the interannual variability of vegetation growth (e.g., onset and offset of the growing season). Similarly, the introduction of the HYDROS river routing scheme, which accounts for water quantity in computing water transport, increases the variability of terrestrial hydrology between seasons. Together, these improvements will provide a more balanced and dynamically coherent initial state, ultimately strengthening seasonal prediction skill and offering potential benefits for future applications on decadal time scales.

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